

Deliverable D16.1

The AAI for TREs Blueprint, first version

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1. Executive Summary

The mission of EOOSC-ENTRUST is to create a European network of trusted research environments (TREs) for sensitive data and to drive European interoperability through the joint development of a common blueprint for federated data access and analysis. This document presents the Authentication, Authorization, and Accounting Infrastructure (AAAI) Blueprint for TREs, a critical component designed to complement the broader TRE architecture by addressing the unique challenges of managing sensitive data, esp. controlling access to them.

Recognizing that the current landscape of TREs is fragmented—with researchers encountering a multitude of disparate systems and providers struggling with incompatible technology and governance frameworks—the AAAI Blueprint builds upon the established AARC Blueprint Architecture and its guidelines. However, the demanding requirements of TREs necessitate targeted enhancements. Specifically, the blueprint extends the traditional framework through four key improvements:

1. **Account Creation:** Secure and efficient processes for provisioning user identities that are tailored to the operational context of TREs.
2. **Identity Vetting:** Rigorous verification methods that ensure users are who they claim to be, thereby facilitating reliable access across national borders.
3. **Attribute-Based Access Control (ABAC):** A fine-grained authorisation model that evaluates not only the conventional subject, object, and operation but also the surrounding environment, thereby centralizing and standardizing policy decisions.
4. **Accounting Layer:** An advanced framework for monitoring, auditing, and tracking usage, which is essential for identifying and responding to potential violations or unauthorized access.

These enhancements are the direct result of a detailed analysis of TRE requirements, also included and addressing heightened security needs, improved interoperability, and stringent accountability. The outcome is a comprehensive set of requirements and recommendations that any AAAI implementation must fulfill, ensuring that the security infrastructure is both robust and adaptable to the evolving landscape of sensitive data management.

This document represents the first version of the AAAI Blueprint. As the project progresses, further iterations are planned for years two and three, which will incorporate refinements based on implementation experiences and emerging best practices. Detailed discussions of the identified areas for improvement and the proposed next steps are provided in Chapter 9, ensuring that the blueprint remains dynamic and responsive to future challenges.

2. Contribution towards project objectives

With this deliverable, the project has reached or the deliverable has contributed to the following objectives/key results:

[Select 'Yes' (at least one) if the deliverable contributed to the key result, otherwise, select 'No'.]

	Key Result No and description	Contributed
Objective 1 Create a European network of Trusted Research Environments, linked to EOSC and EuroHPC, to enable transnational collaborative research on sensitive or restricted data.	1. A catalogue of suitable national or institutional TREs as part of the EOSC offering (WP10/11/12, WP13/14/15)	No
	2. A 'starter pack' of exemplar projects to demonstrate how networks of TREs can address European research priorities (WP4/5/6, WP7/8/9)	No
	3. European researchers are aware of capabilities through communication and outreach events (WP4/5/6) and materials delivered to support national TRE training programmes (WP4/5/6, WP13/14/15)	No
	4. Enable federated use via standards and technology for trusted researcher identity, data use and data access linked to developing European framework for trusted electronic identification of individuals (WP16/17/18)	Yes
	5. Enable researchers and software developers to deploy across multiple TREs via secure FAIR digital objects and workflows (WP16/17/18)	No
	6. EuroHPC capacity that meets the need for secure exascale and GPU (e.g., AI) computing can be identified and connected using the EOSC-ENTRUST framework (WP10/11/12, WP13/14/15).	No
Objective 2 Trusted Research Environment providers implement, validate, and promote their capabilities through a	1. An established European network of national and institutional TRE Providers (WP10/11/12)	No
	2. A service blueprint that allows technical interoperability between TRE based on the EOSC Interoperability framework (WP13/14/15)	No
	3. National and institutional TREs consistently set out their capabilities with common representation for validated legal, operational, semantics and technical aspects (WP10/11/12).	No
	4. Define the security baseline and auditing procedures	No

<p>European framework using common standards and shared legal, operational and technical language.</p>	<p>for TREs to support the Five Safes¹ principles and capture requirements in guidelines for FAIR sensitive data in EOSC (WP13/14/15)</p>	
	<p>5. Drive TRE composability via policy and process interoperability and set out an EOSC compliant governance model for a TRE services network (WP10/11/12, WP13/14/15).</p>	<p>No</p>
<p>Objective 3</p> <p>National funders and governments understand the network of TRE capabilities serving their needs, and how TREs support their national priorities and their contributions to selected transnational programmes</p>	<p>1. A machine-readable catalogue of TRE capabilities allowing detailed, comparative analysis of technical capabilities and identification of gaps (WP10/11/12, WP13/14/15).</p>	<p>No</p>
	<p>2. Policy briefs on the capabilities of the European TRE Provider Forum (WP4/5/6, WP10/11/12) and Use Cases of their application in research domains of high societal impact (WP7/8/9).</p>	<p>No</p>
	<p>3. Connection between the EOSC-ENTRUST Provider Forum and the European Data Spaces (WP1/2/3, WP4/5/6).</p>	<p>No</p>
<p>Objective 4</p> <p>The European Network of Trusted Research Environments (ENTRUST) is embedded in the European Open Science Cloud and the European Data Spaces and fosters an</p>	<p>1. National and organisational providers are incorporated into EOSC via national members and the European network forms part of EOSC long-term strategy (WP1/2/3, WP4/5/6).</p>	<p>No</p>
	<p>2. The emerging European Data Spaces build their capabilities on the network of existing and developing TRE providers (WP4/5/6).</p>	<p>No</p>
	<p>3. Technological developments required by one Data Space activity can be directed to a forum of TRE specialists, reducing the need for duplication and coordinating investment in foundational technologies (WP10/11/12).</p>	<p>No</p>

¹ Ritchie, F. (2017, September). The "Five Safes": A framework for planning, designing and evaluating data access solutions. Paper presented at Data for Policy 2017, London, UK

ecosystem of public, private and joint-venture providers of TRE services.	4. A driver project to demonstrate opportunities for public-private partnerships (WP7/8/9)	No
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3. Definitions / Glossary

See [1] for the EOSC-ENTRUST glossary.

AAAI

Authentication, Authorization, Auditing/Account Infrastructure

AARC

Authentication and Authorisation for Research and Collaboration. The H2020 project (with a follow-up of AARC2 and the currently running AARC TREE) played a key role in developing a reference blueprint - known as the AARC Blueprint Architecture - that guides secure authentication and authorization practices within research infrastructures and EOSC.

ABAC

Attribute-Based Access Control

Accounting

The act of collecting information on resource usage for the purpose of trend analysis, auditing, billing, or cost allocation. [6]

AEGIS

AARC Engagement Group for Infrastructures

Auditing

The act of reviewing accounting records, procedures, and activities to ensure compliance with established policies, standards, and regulations.

Bona-Fide Researcher, Bona-Fide Rights

A user that has been verified as a researcher in the scientific community [7]

BPA

Blueprint architecture

Data Applicant

An organization, institution, or individual that formally requests access to data housed within a Trusted Research Environment (TRE)

Data Consumer

Academic researchers or commercial researchers [2]

Data Controller

According to Article 4(7) of the GDPR, a Data Controller is defined as “the natural or legal person, public authority, agency or other body which, alone or jointly with others, determines the purposes and means of the processing of personal data.”

In a less formal way, the data controller is usually a person or an institution responsible for deciding why and how personal data is processed, and for ensuring that the processing complies with the GDPR's requirements.

Data Custodian

Defined in [2] as responsible for curating and maintaining complete, accurate and useful sets of public data (a technical branch of data controllership, perhaps)

Data Provider

An organisation, institution, or individual that provides the data to a TRE, this may include public health registries [3]; members of the public, data controllers, and data custodians [2]

Data Repository

An institution that stores the data

Data Sharing Agreement

Agreement between a Data Controller and a Data Repository, outlines the terms and conditions for sharing data, including licensing, access controls, and data use limitations

Data Transfer Agreement

An agreement between the Data Controller and Data Applicant when data is physically transferred to the applicant. This type of agreement outlines the responsibilities and security measures required for handling the transferred data.

Data Use Agreement

An agreement between the Data Controller and Data Applicant when the applicant accesses and uses data on its original premises, such as within a TRE maintained by the data holder. This ensures that data remains under the custodianship of the provider while the applicant is granted controlled access.

eID

Electronic identification scheme following the eIDAS Regulation [8]

eIDAS

Electronic IDentification, Authentication, and Trust Services, EU Regulations [8] [9]

EDIF

European Digital Identity Framework [9]

EKYC

Electronic Know Your Customer, automated process through which entities can perform customer identity verification digitally

FURMS

Fenix User and Resource Management Service

GA4GH

Global Alliance for Genomics and Health

GDI

Genomic Data Infrastructure

GDPR

General Data Protection Regulation

IdP	Identity Provider
MFA	Multi-factor authentication
OPA	Open Policy Agent
PEP	Policy Enforcement Point
PDP	Policy Decision Point
PIP	Policy Information Point
PAP	Policy Administration Point
RBAC	Role-Based Access Control
REMS	Resource Entitlement Management System
SGAS	Swedish Grid Accounting System
SIEM	Security information and event management
SP	Service Provider
SPE	Secure Processing Environment
TRE	Trusted Research Environment

4. Introduction / Background

The mission of EOSC-ENTRUST project is to create a European network of Trusted Research Environments (TREs) for sensitive data and to drive European interoperability by joint development of a common blueprint for federated data access and analysis.

Today, while a significant number of TREs are in operation, the landscape remains fragmented. Researchers encounter a variety of disparate systems and access procedures, and providers face the challenge of managing federated access across multiple, often incompatible, technology and governance frameworks. This fragmentation underscores the need for a unified approach that not only standardizes access protocols but also

accommodates the stringent security and operational requirements associated with sensitive data.

EOSC-ENTRUST brings together providers and developers of operational Trusted Research Environments from 15 European countries with a shared goal to implement, validate and promote their capabilities through a common European framework using shared standards and common legal, operational, and technical language.

The AAI Blueprint for TREs aims to provide an integrated architecture for the authentication, authorisation, accounting, and auditing of TREs. It builds on the established AARC Blueprint Architecture (AARC BPA) [4] and the related guidelines [5] as a mandatory starting point for developing the EOSC-ENTRUST AAI. However, TREs dealing with sensitive data introduce additional challenges that require tailored enhancements beyond the conventional AARC approach.

In this context, deliverable D16.1 focuses on the Authentication, Authorization, and Accounting Infrastructure (AAI) as a crucial, complementary component of the overall TRE architecture outlined in D13.4 [25]. Taking into account the unique requirements imposed by the sensitive nature of the data, the AAI Blueprint for TREs extends the AARC Blueprint by incorporating the following four key enhancements:

1) Account Creation

Establishes secure, streamlined procedures for provisioning user accounts tailored to the operational context of TREs.

2) Identity Vetting

Implements rigorous identity verification processes to ensure that only duly authenticated users are granted access, thereby reinforcing trust in the system.

3) Attribute-Based Access Control (ABAC)

Adopts advanced access control mechanisms that evaluate user attributes and contextual factors, enabling fine-grained permission management.

4) Accounting Layer

Develops an enhanced framework for monitoring, recording, and auditing access and usage activities, ensuring transparency and compliance with security requirements.

By integrating these enhancements, the EOSC-ENTRUST AAI Blueprint not only adheres to the mandatory foundation provided by the AARC Blueprint Architecture but also evolves it to meet the specific demands of TREs. The introduction of secure account creation establishes a robust process for provisioning user identities, ensuring consistency and security from the outset. Strengthened identity vetting is designed to verify that users are

who they claim to be, thereby facilitating reliable access across national borders and diverse governance frameworks.

Attribute-Based Access Control (ABAC) is employed to enable fine-grained contextualized authorisation decisions. By considering not only the traditional factors—such as the subject, object, and operation—but also the broader environmental context (e.g. time of day, geographic location), ABAC supports centralized management of authorisation policies. This approach relieves individual services from implementing their own decision mechanisms and guarantees uniformity in policy enforcement across the federation.

The addition of an advanced accounting layer serves a dual purpose. It provides continuous monitoring for any potential violations or unauthorized access while also maintaining comprehensive audit trails for tracking incidents when they occur. Moreover, by offering federated points for critical components like identity vetting and authorisation policy management, the blueprint implementation will improve interoperability. This ensures that all services within the federation can rely on consistent functionality and decision-making, ultimately reinforcing the overall security and operational integrity of TREs. Services do not need to implement such components themselves and they can trust that the functionality and decisions are the same across the whole federation.

This AAI Blueprint represents the year-one version of our effort, establishing a solid foundation based on the AARC Blueprint while addressing the unique challenges of TREs. The AAI Blueprint for TREs will undergo regular revisions and refinement, with a yearly publication. Some areas of interest have already been identified, and these are discussed in detail in Chapter 9, Next steps.

5. Requirements for AAI

In this chapter, we define the requirements of EOSC-ENTRUST AAI and describe the vital features and standards for secure and user-friendly access within the EOSC-ENTRUST federation. We start by stating that the AAI MUST implement the AARC Blueprint Architecture and the related guidelines and then extend that baseline with further requirements. The requirements were collected by the work package members from other work packages in the EOSC-ENTRUST project as well as other sources the work package members were familiar with. These requirements establish a framework to ensure reliable security, compliance, and efficient user interactions by covering functional needs like identity assurance and access control and non-functional needs like scalability and privacy. Some of the collected requirements overlapped, so a curated list of final requirements is found in Tables 1 and 2 in this document. Table 1 collects functional requirements and Table 2 non-functional ones.

5.1 Overview of the requirements

Below is an overview of the curated requirements. The requirements are assigned an identifier (R1, R2, ...Rn) for unambiguous referencing. The key words “MUST”, “MUST NOT”, “REQUIRED”, “SHALL”, “SHALL NOT”, “SHOULD”, “SHOULD NOT”, “RECOMMENDED”, “MAY”, and “OPTIONAL” in this document are to be interpreted as described in RFC2119 [24].

We identified five groups within the requirements: user identity, access control, accounting and auditing, and infrastructure. The groups roughly line up with the layers represented by different colours in the blueprint in chapter 6. The same colour schema is followed in Tables 1 and 2. In this chapter, we first give an overview of how the requirements fit into these groups and then expand on each requirement in chapters 5.1.1 and 5.1.2.

User identity related requirements

Requirements R9, R13, R14, R15, R21, R22 and R36 concern user identity. They define how user accounts are created and linked together as well as how user identities are verified (identity vetting). They concern User Identity and Community Attribute Services layers in the blueprint.

Access control related requirements

One of the primary functions of the AAI is access control and authorisation. Requirements R9, R14, R17, R18, R20 as well as R11 and R12 concern access control and authorisation with R17 being the most important one and the others complementing it.

Accounting and Auditing related requirements

The requirements R2, R3, R4, R6, R7 and R8 form the basis of accounting and auditing in the EOOSC-ENTRUST federation. Together they form the Accounting layer in the Blueprint.

Infrastructure related requirements

Requirements R23, R24, R27 and R33 deal with Access Protocol Translation layer in the blueprint. They define how home organisations and services can integrate with the AAI and what kind of access protocols should be used.

Agreements and entitlements related requirements

Accepting agreements and policies (such as acceptable use policy) and completing trainings came up as requirements for the AAI. These are handled in Requirements R11 and R12.

The AAI itself has regulations and policies it must follow. These are discussed in requirements R3 and R16.

5.1.1 Functional requirements

ID	Name	Requirement Level	Description
R2	Technology-Agnostic Accounting Data Collection	MUST	The AAAI must ensure accounting data collection is independent of specific technologies (e.g., Perun, SATOSA, SimpleSAMLphp, Keycloak). API-based data collection will enable seamless interoperability, allowing data to be aggregated, analysed, and reported in a unified manner regardless of the underlying AAAI technology
R4	Data Analytics and Reporting	SHOULD	The AAAI should provide analytics tools for monitoring accounting data, detecting patterns, risks, or misconfigurations in real-time
R6	Access Control for Accounting Data	MUST	The AAAI must support roles and access levels for who can view or modify accounting data, ensuring only authorised personnel or services can access sensitive logs
R7	Notifications and Alerts	MAY	The AAAI may support real-time alerts when suspicious activities or anomalies are detected (e.g., failed authentications, access policy violations)
R8	Trace/Audit log	MUST	The AAAI must collect/log detailed information on all authentication and authorisation events, including user identifiers, timestamps, IP addresses, authentication methods, and authorisation decisions. These logs must retain system-generated information that allows the reconstruction of a coherent and complete view of activity (the 'who, what, where, when, why', and 'to whom') for auditing and security incident investigation purposes
R9	MFA	MUST	AAAI must be able to perform MFA when required

R11	Agreements	MUST	AAAI must indicate which agreements the user has accepted
R12	Entitlements	MUST	AAAI must indicate which training the user has passed and use this data for authorisation decisions.
R13	Account Creation	MUST	The AAAI must provide a solution that enables new users to create an account within the EOSC-ENTRUST federation
R14	Identity Assurance	MUST	AAAI must provide a mechanism to verify the authenticity and legitimacy of an individual's identity
R15	Identity Freshness	MUST	AAAI must verify that the users' digital identity is still valid
R16	Anonymisation	SHOULD	AAAI should provide a solution for anonymising users' data
R17	Access Control	MUST	<p>AAAI must offer a way to manage entitlements and permissions of a user to access digital resources such as datasets or a computing services. These permissions and entitlements must be stored and communicated according to community standards implemented in science and e-Infrastructure clusters in Europe. Managing predefined authorisation rules must be included. This includes but is not limited to Bona-Fide rights for access and group membership-based access. Furthermore, users must be able to select which attributes, groups or roles are used for a particular authorisation decision.</p> <p>This requirement deals with user data included</p>

			within the the AAI, not the data it helps to control access to.
R18	Authorisation Delegation	MUST	AAAI must provide a service to TREs for enforcing data permissions, grants, and entitlements of users and projects.
R19	Access Request	MUST	AAAI must provide a solution which allows users/projects to request access to resources and services within a specific TRE
R20	Access Suspension and revocation	MUST	AAAI must provide a solution to deny individual users (or entire IdPs) access to TREs in case of a security incident
R21	Local Accounts	MUST	AAAI must provide a way to manage accounts for users without a home organisation account
R22	Account Linking	SHOULD	AAAI should provide a way to link users' different digital identities into a single account. Linking ORCID specifically is likely to be needed. See also R26 that introduces a unique identifier.
R23	Definition of protocols	MUST	AAAI must provide and document a set of protocols that must be supported by individual SPs/TREs/IdPs in order to integrate with the EOSC-ENTRUST federation
R24	Registering SPs and IdPs	MUST	AAAI must provide a solution for integrating new SPs and IdPs.

R27	Smart Discovery	SHOULD	The IdP discovery should be “smart enough” to quickly and easily take a user to their appropriate home IdP
R33	Non-web use cases	MUST	The AAI system must enable authentication and authorisation via non-web use cases, as many interactions between clients and servers are via the user’s command line or via interacting applications using APIs
R35	AARC BPA Compliance	MUST	The AAI system must comply with the AARC Blueprint Architecture [4], which serves as the baseline architecture for the EOSC AAI (EOSC AAI Architecture 2022 [11]), and adhere to the related interoperability guidelines [5] endorsed by AEGIS [12].
R36	Identity Wallets	SHOULD ²	The AAI system should integrate wallet-based authentication to align with eIDASv2 regulations. This integration should support the EU Digital Wallet and national wallets, ensuring compliance with eIDASv2 standards.

Table 1: Functional requirements

The requirements have been color coded to match layers in the blueprint (see Fig 1)

Requirement R2 Technology-Agnostic Accounting Data Collection normalises the collected data to be independent of AAI systems by using an API-based data collection model. This enables both internal AAI services (e.g. Community Attribute Services, Proxy, etc.) and external consumer services to send accounting information to the accounting service regardless of their infrastructure or technology stacks.

Centralized accounting data only achieves its full potential when paired with robust analysis capabilities. Requirement R4 mandates that the EOSC-ENTRUST AAI SHOULD incorporate analytical tools designed to identify risks, intrusions, and other anomalies in normal operations. To further enhance threat detection and response, the accounting service SHOULD integrate with SIEM tools.

² The Identity wallets are expected to become mandatory in the next version of this Blueprint, but at this moment the whole eWallet ecosystem (and also the general AAI Blueprint) are not mature enough to make them a mandatory requirement.

Requirement R6 mandates having access controls for accounting data. The accounting service **MUST** support roles and access levels allowing different users different access to the accounting data. Access **MUST** be granted only to authorised personnel and any changes to existing accounting data **MUST** leave an audit trail.

Requirement R7 covers real-time notifications and alerts based on accounting data. These can be valuable in detecting risks and issues, but care must be taken to define conditions to maintain a good signal-to-noise ratio and to prevent false alerts.

Requirement R8 mandates minimal requirements for what accounting data **MUST** be collected. In short, the collected data should be sufficient to answer the questions of who, what, where, when, why and to whom about any activity or decision taking place in the EOSC-ENTRUST federation. Care must be taken to minimise the amount of sensitive data included in accounting data and to comply with any relevant privacy regulations. Opaque identifiers should be used whenever possible.

Requirement R9 mandates performing multi-factor authentication (MFA) when required by the service. This is covered by BPA Guideline AARC-G029. We extend this by making the ability to perform MFA a **MUST** requirement rather than **SHOULD**. It is important to note that MFA should only be performed once per login for usability reasons, so if the user's home organisation already performs MFA then the AAI should accept that and not require a second MFA.

Users may be required to review and accept various agreements and policies before accessing services in the EOSC-ENTRUST federation. Requirement R11 specifies that the AAI **MUST** collect and maintain a list of agreements the user has accepted and use that to support authorisation decisions. These **MUST** be expressed using entitlements similar to how group memberships are expressed in AARC-G069 and resource capabilities are expressed in AARC-G027.

Many external consumer services may require service-specific training before allowing users access to the service. Similarly, an EOSC-ENTRUST federation-wide initial training may be required of all users. Requirement R12 mandates that the AAI **MUST** collect and maintain information on what training the user has completed and use that information to support authorisation decisions. These **MUST** be expressed using entitlements similar to how group memberships are expressed in AARC-G069 and resource capabilities are expressed in AARC-G027.

Requirement R14 mandates a mechanism to perform identity vetting as a **MUST**. This means the AAI **MUST** have a way to tie a user account to a natural person with a high level of assurance. The EOSC-ENTRUST federation will handle sensitive data, so the ability to

ensure who is behind a user account is important. This requirement forms the Identity vetting component in the blueprint. Identity vetting is split between Community Attribute Services and User Identity layers because it can be performed by either a service belonging to the AAAI or an external service.

Requirement R15 mandates ensuring identity freshness. This means making sure that user attributes such as affiliations are up to date. Usually, this is implemented by requiring users to refresh the attributes (e.g. by performing federated login again) after a given time frame. A common time frame is once a year (every 12 months).

Requirement R16 concerns anonymising user data. Requirement R3 is also related to this. The AAAI MUST define and document policies and procedures for compliance with regulations and anonymising user data. It may not be possible to anonymise accounting data, but using opaque identifiers should help maximise user data privacy in accounting data.

Requirement R17 deals with access control. This is a complex topic with numerous details. The main requirement is that AAAI MUST be able to make authorisation decisions at the proxy based on predefined access rules. It MUST be possible to define both global rules (that affect all end services) as well as end service-specific rules. This is also covered by BPA Guideline AARC-I047, but we extend it to MUST rather than SHOULD. R17 mandates that at a minimum access rules MUST include the ability to require Bona Fide status from a user or group membership. Other requirements extend this minimum requirement. Requirement R9 mandates that the AAAI MUST be able to require MFA for access. Requirement R14 mandates that AAAI MUST be able to require successful identity vetting for access. Requirements R11 and R12 specify that the AAAI MUST be able to require accepted agreements or passed training courses for access. Finally, R17 mandates that users MUST be able to select which of their attributes are used for a particular access request. This enables using the least amount of privileges required for a task, e.g. a project manager may login as a project member if they do not need manager-level access. Using only required attributes supports user privacy and data minimisation as well.

Requirement R18 mandates that the AAAI MUST provide a way for end services to define access rules mentioned in R17.

Requirement R21 mandates that the AAAI MUST provide a way to manage accounts for users without a home organisation account. This is needed for users coming from smaller public or not-for-profit as well as commercial organisations, as they may not have an account from a federated home organization.

Requirement R22 specifies that the AAAI SHOULD allow users to link multiple external identities into a single identity in the EOSC-ENTRUST federation. This should be implemented according to BPA Guideline AARC-G009. Requirements R13 and R21 are related to this as well and should be taken into consideration when implementing R22.

Requirement R24 mandates a centralised resource register solution for integrating new SPs, IdPs and Attribute Authorities as community attribute services to the AAAI federation.

The expectation of Requirement 27 is that a smart IdP discovery service SHOULD be available to select home IdP based on short lists. Shortlists can be tailored by country, institute, e-infrastructure, research community, project or other clues. This discovery service requirement is covered in guidelines AARC-G061, AARC-G062 and AARC-G063.

Requirement R33 specifies that the AAAI MUST enable access to end services via non-web use cases. This is covered by AARC BPA Guidelines AARC-G004, AARC-G005, AARC-G007 and AARC-G010.

Requirement R36 is a speculative one at this point. Requirement R14 mandates identity vetting, and the most reliable way to do this would be with government-backed electronic identification (eID) as specified by the eIDASv1 regulation [8]. However, this method is not usable for everyone in the EU due to differences in national implementations of eIDASv1. The updated regulation eIDASv2 [9] should ease the use of eIDs by way of digital wallets and enable far wider usage than eIDASv1 did. Wallets and eIDASv2 are not yet usable or available, so R36 specifies that they should be used once they become available.

5.1.2 Non-Functional requirements

ID	Name	Requirement Level	Description
R3	Compliance and Privacy	MUST	The AAAI must comply with privacy regulations (e.g., GDPR) and implement best practices to minimise data exposure. This includes documented data anonymisation, retention policies, and secure storage.
R5	Performance and Scalability	MUST	The AAAI must be able to accommodate a high number of users, services, and communities and must be able to scale as these numbers grow. The AAAI must set performance benchmarks and scalability requirements to handle expected loads (e.g., user authentications, AAAI API calls).

R10	Usability	SHOULD	User experience and ease of use should be evaluated and taken into account when implementing the AAAI for TREs. This is especially important due to the high security requirements for all TREs components, where such security requirements can lead to a cumbersome user experience for end users.
R25	Unique identifier for projects	MUST	The project identifier must be globally recognisable and unique within the Federation
R26	Unique identifier for users	MUST	The user identifier must be globally recognisable and unique within the Federation

Table 2: Non-functional requirements

Requirement R3 mandates that the AAAI MUST comply with various regulations and policies. A complete list of regulations and policies is outside the scope of this document, but AARC BPA Guidelines AARC-G014, AARC-G015, AARC-G016, AARC-G042, and AARC-G071 offer recommendations and templates for various documents the AAAI must provide.

Requirements R25 and R26 mandate that the AAAI MUST provide globally unique identifiers for projects and users, respectively. These both should be issued following AARC BPA Guidelines AARC-G026 and AARC-G031. The identifiers for users should be globally unique, persistent, permanent, and opaque. The identifiers for projects should be globally unique, persistent, and permanent.

6. Blueprint Architecture

Building on the AARC Blueprint Architecture 2019 [4], we have enhanced the AAI by integrating additional Accounting and Auditing components. For a comprehensive comparison, Chapter 7 ('Revisions') details the differences between the EOSC-ENTRUST AAAI for TREs Blueprint and the original AARC Blueprint Architecture, as documented in AARC-BPA-2019-Final.

Figure 1: The AAAI Blueprint³

This diagram illustrates the high-level architecture of the Authentication, Authorization, and Accounting Infrastructure (AAAI) for TREs. The colored parts represent key components: secure account creation (processes for registering and managing user accounts), identity vetting (mechanisms to verify that users are who they claim to be), attribute-based access control (fine-grained authorization based on user attributes and contextual factors), and an advanced accounting layer (for collecting, monitoring, and auditing usage data).

6.1. Authentication

User identity deals with identifying and authenticating users. EOSC-ENTRUST is a closed network, meaning users need an account before being able to become a member and log into a TRE. The *Account Creation* step ensures users have an account that meets the EOSC-ENTRUST requirements or a new one without any access rights is created for them. Due to the sensitivity of the data processed in EOSC-ENTRUST, high-quality *Identity Vetting* is a key part of *Account Creation*. User accounts in EOSC-ENTRUST need to be linked to verified identities of natural persons. *Identity Vetting* should be done using a high assurance electronic method, e.g. eID or a EKYC-process based on government-issued identification documents. Identity vetting can be done either locally by the EOSC-ENTRUST AAAI or by an external service.

³ Original schema taken from AARC Blueprint Architecture and extended

Step-Up Authentication (e.g., multifactor authentication) should primarily be handled by the user's home organization, ensuring that the initial authentication process is secure. When the home organization does not support MFA, the AAAI MUST trigger a backup Step-Up Authentication (the Step up Authn in Fig 1) process to enforce multifactor authentication. Conversely, if MFA has already been successfully completed by the home organization, the AAAI SHOULD NOT require users to perform MFA again.

6.2. Authorisation and Access Control

Authorisation specifies rights/privileges for accessing resources, more formally defining an access policy enforced by *access control* during usage. There are multiple access control models, the recent ones being Role-Based Access Control (RBAC) and Attribute-Based Access Control (ABAC). ABAC is more general than RBAC, it can do everything RBAC can do and more, thus it is recommended by NIST in its publication SP 800-162 [13] for dynamic and complex environments.

ABAC makes access decisions by evaluating rules contained in an access policy against the attributes of:

- *subject* - the user attempting to access a resource
- *object* - the resource being accessed, e.g. a dataset, file, computer, service
- *operation* - the action being attempted e.g. read, delete, view, approve
- *environment* - the context of the access, like time, location or other aspects, e.g. whether it is business hours or a national holiday, whether a state of emergency is declared, whether the price of electric power is high or low, and so on

ABAC recommends the following architecture:

- PEP (Policy Enforcement Point) - enforces policy decisions in response to a request from a subject requesting access to a protected object; the access control decisions are made by the PDP
- PDP (Policy Decision Point) - evaluates incoming requests against policies, returns a Permit/Deny decision
- PIP (Policy Information Point) - the retrieval source of attributes
- PAP (Policy Administration Point) - provides a user interface for creating, managing, testing, and debugging policies, and storing these policies in the appropriate repository

Figure 2: ABAC schema⁴

The diagram above from NIST SP 800-162 shows the components. Decisions are made by Policy Decision Point, which reads policies from Policy Administration Point, reads attributes of subject, object, operation and environment from Policy Information Point, and the decisions are enforced by Policy Enforcement Point.

The components may be centralised or distributed, likely the PEP would be present at each service, PDP may be multiplied and located near PEPs for scalability. The important feature is that a policy is shared from a single source and enforced uniformly.

There are two types of access policies:

- digital policy - access control rules that compile directly into machine executable codes or signals
- metapolicy - a policy about policies, or policy for managing policies, such as assignment of priorities and resolution of conflicts between digital policies

An open-source tool for implementation of ABAC is available in Open Policy Agent (OPA, [14]). OPA is a general-purpose policy engine with a high-level declarative language named Rego for specifying policy as code, and simple APIs to offload policy decision-making from software. OPA accepts data about the request and entity attributes in the form of multiple JSON documents. Its output is a single JSON document, containing at least a boolean flag whether access was granted or denied, but can also contain other data. The Rego language provides the syntax for rules transforming input JSON documents into the output JSON document.

⁴ Figure taken from NIST SP 800-162

The main advantages of specifying a declarative digital access policy as code (compared to hard-coding it in individual software systems) are:

- decouples policy decision-making from policy enforcement
- policy is testable (i.e. it is possible to write unit tests for it)
- policy can be maintained by other administrators than individual software systems, and thus enforced across multiple software systems

6.2.1. The relation of the ABAC model and GA4GH Passport

There are two standards developed for authentication and authorization in the area of genomic data, which are a particular type of sensitive data that may need processing in TREs. These are GA4GH Passport [21] and GA4GH AAI OIDC Profile [22].

GA4GH Passport is a collection of digitally signed documents named Visas, which contain attributes of the accessing subject (user) like their affiliation and roles in organizations, accepted terms and policies, researcher status, and decisions made by Data Access Committees (DACs) about granting access to datasets to that specific user.

In the ABAC model, GA4GH Passport is an attribute repository supplying attributes to a Policy Information Point, that joins them with other attributes and provides them to a Policy Decision Point to make the final access decision.

The decisions made by Data Access Committees and the decisions made by Policy Decision Points are different types of decisions. The decisions made by DACs are authorizations made by a dedicated committee granting access to a particular dataset, usually valid for a particular researcher only. They are neither a sufficient condition nor a necessary condition for the decisions made by Policy Decision Points. They are merely subject attributes taken into consideration by PDPs, which also consider attributes of the accessed object, operation and environment, and also whether that particular DAC is authorised for granting access to that particular dataset, before making the final decision.

The final access decision made by a Policy Decision Point then needs to be transferred from the PDP into a Policy Enforcement Point to enforce it. It is known that the U.S. NIH encodes these access decisions in a custom type of Visa, but generally, there is no need to use the Passport standard for this transfer if the PDP and PEP belong to the same administration domain and the encoding of the final access decisions can be implementation-dependent.

6.2.2. ABAC in EOOSC-ENTRUST Federation of TREs

In the **EOOSC-ENTRUST federation of TREs**, the access control should be based on ABAC, because it takes into account not only the properties of the user, the accessed object, and

the operation, but also the properties of the environment, which will have a significant influence in access decisions in TREs. For example, the fact that a data use agreement needed for processing data was signed is neither the attribute of the user, nor the object, nor the operation.

These access control decisions would be made at the granularity of individual objects (such as datasets, specific service components, or even the TRE login) rather than at the level of entire services, as is the case in the AARC BPA.

Figure 3: EOSC-ENTRUST Infrastructure architecture⁵

The Policy Information Point in the EOSC-ENTRUST federation would need to collect all data needed for access decisions. In *Figure 3* we present some sources of such information:

- Authentication infrastructure, Certification and Training Registry, and Users Registry may supply attributes for users
- Dataset Registry may supply attributes for datasets as accessed objects
- Projects Registry may supply attributes for the environment about projects
- Federation Participants Registry may supply attributes for the environment, namely
 - Index Services
 - Software Services
 - Federation Services

The figure does not mention a registry for established agreements - **Data Sharing Agreements**, **Data Transfer Agreements**, and **Data Use Agreements** - which may be taken

⁵ The *Figure 6.2.1 EOSC-ENTRUST Infrastructure architecture* from Deliverable D13.4 [25]

into account when making decisions about access to datasets. Perhaps this would be part of the Dataset Registry.

6.2.3. Authorisation Use Cases

Use cases for authorisation in federated TREs are not clear. Here are the two use cases identified by the GA4GH Data Use and Research Identity workstream in 2017 in preparation for the development of GA4GH Passports:

Researcher Identity: These specify the collection of researchers that may access the dataset at any given time, and the credentials they must supply. For example, it may be the case that only researchers that are members of a consortium may access a dataset for the first year after generation.

Data Use: When human subjects are consented as participants in a study, the informed consent form specifies appropriate restrictions on secondary data use. For example, it may stipulate that the data may be used only for “cancer research in a non-profit setting.” Similarly, data owners may place additional restrictions on data use.

It is worth noting that the specification of GA4GH Passport in its latest version 1.2.1 [15] does not fully support any of these use cases. The Researcher Identity use case is not supported in GA4GH Passport because the information about consortium membership and the first year after generation limit cannot be expressed as Visas in a Passport. The Data Use use case is not supported because the information “cancer research in a non-profit setting” cannot be expressed. The Visa types defined in GA4GH Passport specification do not cover types for such information.

It is likely that these two use cases may exist in a federation of TREs, thus the data needed for their access decisions need to be provided by some registries. Other use cases would probably be identified later.

6.3. Accounting and Auditing

Accounting is the process of collecting data to enable *Auditing*. This data should be able to answer the questions of who, what, where, when, why and to whom. For example, “Manager added User to group Researchers. Manager is allowed to do this because Manager is the group owner of the group Researchers.”

Accounting is closely linked to several components in the blueprint. Therefore a centralized service, *Accounting Services*, where different components can send their accounting data is needed. Most of the accounting data collected is expected to come from the authorisation components of the AAI system, especially PEP and PDP as described in chapter 6.2

Authorisation and Access Control. Using an API-based data collection model enables both other components of the AAAI services (e.g. Community Attribute Services, Proxy, etc.) and end services to send accounting information to *Accounting Services* regardless of their infrastructure or technology stacks.

Collecting accounting data over a large federation can result in unmanageable amounts of data. To avoid this, only authentication, authorisation, and access control events should be collected. Individual components or services can then collect more data as needed. That is to say, any event involving multiple components should be logged centrally while events inside individual components can be logged internally. This approach also mitigates the risk of creating a single, large collection of user data that would be an attractive target for attacks.

All logging collected over all components of the blueprint should be correlated, so that events stemming from an authentication event can be traced and tied together afterwards. This correlation should enable the tracking of actions across different systems, allowing for a comprehensive view of user activity. Relevant information to be captured includes timestamps, the user initiating the event, the resources accessed, the actions performed, and the outcomes of those actions.

Accounting data should not be stored indefinitely and should be subject to a retention policy. The length of accounting data storage should be unified across all services and components in the EOSC-ENTRUST federation. Accounting data can be divided into categories based on age to lessen data storage and computation needs. The most recent data, called hot data, should be indexed and readily available. Intermediate data, called warm data, does not need to be indexed and readily available but should be accessible via the auditing UI. Old data, called cold data, can be encrypted and moved to separate storage to be stored until the retention period is passed and the data is deleted.

Auditing is the process of reviewing data collected in *Accounting*. Access to accounting data and by extension to *Auditing* should be restricted and controlled. A UI for reviewing accounting data should be offered. This UI should offer data analytics and reporting and may offer notification and alerts. Potential choices for suitable software are discussed in chapter 9.

The main reasons to review accounting data are to ensure compliance or to investigate anomalous behaviour in EOSC-ENTRUST. The accounting data collected centrally should offer a view into what services or systems a user (or users originating from one home organisation for example) has accessed. Further data can then be requested from those services or systems based on correlation IDs.

7. Revisions since AARC-BPA-2019-Final

The EOSC-ENTRUST AAI architecture introduces new components and adjustments to the original AARC BPA 2019 to better support the specific needs of the EOSC-ENTRUST federation. These revisions ensure enhanced security, compliance, and operational efficiency for managing user identities, authentication, and data handling within the system. The key revisions are as follows:

Account Creation:

A new Account Creation process has been added to the Community Attribute Service layer. This ensures that users have valid accounts before accessing member TREs in EOSC-ENTRUST. The process verifies whether a user has an existing account or whether a new one needs to be created with restricted access rights.

Identity Vetting:

The revised architecture introduces Identity Vetting for flexible integration with external identity vetting services, ensuring that identity verification can be handled through high-assurance electronic methods, such as eID or eKYC processes, that are essential for EOSC-ENTRUST's sensitive data processing requirements.

Attribute-Based Access Control:

Finer-grained authorization on the level of individual objects instead of services has been added.

Introduction of the Accounting Layer:

A significant revision to the original AARC BPA is the introduction of an Accounting Layer, which includes both the Accounting Service and the Auditing components. The Accounting Service collects and aggregates data from various components of the architecture, answering critical questions related to user actions and permissions. This centralised service enables better monitoring and ensures that all user actions are properly recorded for auditing purposes.

The Auditing component, closely tied to the Accounting Layer, enables the review and analysis of accounting data to ensure compliance with security policies and detect anomalous behaviour. This audit process is essential for maintaining transparency and accountability within the EOSC-ENTRUST federation, particularly in environments with high-security requirements.

8. Conclusions

This document describes the year-one version of the AAI for TREs Blueprint. This blueprint will be evaluated in practice during the project's second year, as other work

packages implement their demonstrators and we begin integrating the AAAI enhancements to support them. This hands-on evaluation will provide critical insights and feedback that will guide the refinement of the year 2 version of this blueprint.

9. Next Steps

The most important next step is the next version of this blueprint. Under the project plan, it is scheduled for year 2, after gathering practical experience through the demonstrators the other work packages are planning.

This blueprint provides the requirements and guidelines for the AAAI in the EOSC-ENTRUST federation but omits implementation details such as software choices or policy texts. These details will need to be settled as part of implementing the demonstrators on the AAAI side. As part of this, at least the following policies should be defined:

- Processing of personal data
- Privacy policy
- Acceptable use policy
- Data retention policy

There are a plethora of technical and implementation details that are beyond the scope of this blueprint. AARC BPA solves this problem by having separate guidelines for technical and implementation details. We should adopt this same approach in EOSC-ENTRUST, making writing these guidelines an important next step. One example of a necessary separate guideline document is the accounting service. This guideline needs to define in detail the data collected by the accounting service as well as retention periods and other details.

Software solutions for storing accounting data and performing auditing will need to be evaluated and selected as part of the future pilot implementation within the EOSC-ENTRUST project. From an architectural perspective, the list below is provided only to illustrate that open-source options are viable, though the final selection is not limited to open-source software. Potential software stacks include the ELK stack (Elasticsearch, Kibana, and Logstash), Graylog, and Opensearch. Data similar to the accounting data outlined in this document is often collected for billing purposes. It may be worthwhile to investigate whether software designed for billing data collection could be repurposed for accounting data collection as well. For example, FURMS [16] from the Fenix Infrastructure and the Swedish Grid Accounting System (SGAS) [17] are such solutions. Leveraging software originally developed for billing may create synergies between accounting and billing data collection, depending on how TREs manage billing for users.

In addition to software selection and other implementation details, the accounting service described here and in future guidelines should be evaluated against security guidelines. One such guideline is the EOOSC Security Operational Baseline [23].

GA4GH has identified consortiums of organisations as a use case for authorisation decisions. While the AAAI already defines group memberships as a piece of information for authorisation decisions, consortium memberships for organisations are different and may need extra functionality. This is something that should be explored and clarified for future versions of this blueprint.

GA4GH Passports and Visas are already in use at some TREs (e.g. CSC Sensitive Data services) and can be managed through software like REMS [18]. Including them in EOOSC-ENTRUST AAAI must be considered. They are also going to be part of projects such as GDI [19] and were also mentioned in the preparation of Bigpicture [20]. The EOOSC-ENTRUST AAAI must be built in collaboration with such projects and must be compatible with them. This is something that should be taken into account and ensured in the coming versions of this blueprint.

Requirements R25 and R26 define identifiers for both projects and users respectively. The EOOSC-ENTRUST overall architecture blueprint places “Project registry” and “User registry” inside “Federation Services” but outside the AAAI. This is something that should be clarified in future versions of this blueprint and the overall blueprint. The current plan is to implement AAAI services needed by EOOSC-ENTRUST according to the architecture blueprint on top of Life Science AAI, which provides Life Science ID as globally unique, persistent, permanent and opaque identifier for users. It might be more beneficial to use this as the identifier for users in the EOOSC-ENTRUST federation rather than building a new user registry.

Our approach aligns with and complements the objectives of SIESTA and TITAN projects. SIESTA focuses on enabling the secure re-use of sensitive research data by establishing trusted data sharing practices and services to ease the secure sharing through state-of-the-art anonymization techniques. TITAN has the overall objective of enriching the EOOSC Interoperability Framework (IF) by developing a software platform solution for confidential collaboration and privacy-preserving data processing. Both projects could benefit from the AAAI for TREs architecture and implementation as they both need strong identity proofing and access control services. We plan to start closer work with the TITAN project for, e.g., to collect additional requirements that come from their work on the confidential collaboration and also to test our accounting/auditing enhancement against their plans for the auditing mechanisms for sensitive data and secure data sharing.

10. Impact

This document delivers the year-one version of the AAI for TREs Blueprint and takes the first steps towards completing project objective 1.4: “Enable federated use via standards and technology for trusted researcher identity, data use and data access linked to developing European framework for trusted electronic identification of individuals.” While the full impact of this blueprint cannot be definitively assessed at this early stage, it is expected to set the standards, protocols, and practices that will underpin the integration of services and home organisations not only into the EOSC-ENTRUST federation. In the long term, this work will contribute to establishing a cohesive, secure, and interoperable infrastructure for TREs across Europe, laying the groundwork for enhanced collaboration and effective management of sensitive research data.

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